

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the requirements for improving the quality of education in the higher education system, reforms in the process of reforming the higher education system, the creation of a new generation of educational and regulatory documents, taking into account the student's labor intensity, the development of academic and professional flexibility of graduates, the introduction of a credit-modular system when introducing intensive methods of knowledge acquisition.*

Keywords: *knowledge, intensity, credit, personnel, competence, demand, education, education reform, quality.*

In the process of reforming the higher education system of Uzbekistan, the introduction of the national qualification framework started a new era in the training of highly educated personnel.

In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. Pursuant to Order No. 357, from the 2020-2021 academic year, higher education institutions of the republic switched to the credit-module system. [1]

Systematic development of higher educational institutions that train pedagogic personnel and improvement of their management, development of modern educational programs with the introduction of advanced foreign experiences, raising the training of highly qualified professional personnel to a new level, as well as education in the field of pedagogy, in order to ensure the harmony of science and practice, on June 21, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions training pedagogic personnel" Decision No. PQ-289 was adopted. In accordance with the decision, to revise the educational programs of higher education institutions training pedagogues in cooperation with foreign experts and to align them with the National Qualification Framework, the International Standard Classification of Education (MSKO-2011), curricula and educational programs coordination tasks were set for each other.[2]

Today's reforms include creating a new generation of educational and regulatory documents, taking into account the student's labor intensity, developing the academic and professional flexibility of graduates, introducing the credit-module system in the introduction of intensive methods of knowledge acquisition.

Academic credits were first introduced in US universities in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. The organization of educational content and programs in credits, independent planning

of the educational process, made it possible to make fundamental changes in monitoring and evaluation systems, and created ample conditions for improving educational technologies.

ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) was introduced in 1989 as part of the Erasmus program and is a part of the Socrat program. The European credit system has been successfully tested, and currently all European higher education institutions are using the ECTS system.

Initially, ECTS was used to calculate and transfer credits when transferring students from one higher education institution to another. This system has helped the recognition of other higher education institutions, thus increasing the quality of European higher education institutions and increasing the scale of student mobility. As a result of the growing importance of the credit system, it became a regional, national and European level system as one of the most important tasks of the Bologna Declaration signed in June 1999.

Although ECTS was put into practice as a recommendatory system in the Bologna Declaration, later it became popular in the entire European higher education system. The ECTS system is considered one of the main systems operating in Europe today and serves as a basis for the creation of normative documents of higher education.

As a result of using the ECTS system, it has been shown that it has the following advantages:

- recognition of simplified qualifications among higher education institutions;
- transparency of student workload;
- adaptability to reforms in the higher education system;
- The breadth of flexibility in learning programs in the educational trajectory.

The ECTS system makes learning programs easier and is convenient for all types of programs. ECTS creates ample conditions for academic mobility between countries, as well as between different universities. In addition, the system is also a self-learning system. That's why ECTS stands for European Credit Transfer and Collection System.

The main features of the European credit transfer and collection system are as follows:

- ECTS credits;
- Student load;
- Educational indicators;
- ECTS assessment rating scale.

The credit module system performs two main tasks:

First, to continue studying on the basis of the terms of academic mobility and flexibility on the basis of credits received from another higher education institution (or another faculty),

The second is accumulative education. A student can receive education in different periods of time, change universities and in different periods. If there is no specified expiration date for certain results (for example, because the course is out of date), credits will be accumulated until the student has earned the required amount to obtain the appropriate academic degree (bachelor's, master's). Of course, the ability to transfer credit and accumulate credits depends on trust between universities and the compatibility of academic programs.

The maximum volume of the educational load, which includes all types of classroom and non-auditory work, is set at 54 hours per week. The maximum volume of classroom training in the daytime form of study is defined as 30 hours per week. One credit is considered to be equal to 30 academic hours. The size of the auditorium and independent education load is 50/50. A student earns 30 credits per semester and a total of 240 credits over 8 semesters.

When the standard term of study is 4 years, the educational process should be 120 weeks, when the standard term of the academic year is 1 year, the educational process should be 30 weeks. The standard terms of this study apply to all forms of education (full-time education, evening education, part-time education):

\Standard term of study:

Study periods	For full-time education*	For evening education*	For part-time education*
Theoretical education and scientific activity*	40-60%	40-60%	40-60%
Continuous independent education and scientific activity	40:60% to 50:50%	40:60%	20:80%
Vacation	10-30%	10-30%	10-30%
Scientific practice (internship)	15-25%	15-30%	15-30%

Below is the methodology of educational programs.

Representation of the load of higher professional education programs in credit units

Credit units of higher professional education programs are based on the following:

1. One credit corresponds to 30 academic hours in the total load and the duration is 40 minutes.
2. The maximum weekly workload of a student is up to 54 academic hours, which is expressed in 1.8 credit units.
3. When granting credits to subjects, it is ensured that study hours are carried out in the amount of 30 hours per week in accordance with the established rules. Subjects, course projects, and other graded work are taken into account when awarding credits.
4. One week of practice is represented by 1.8 credits.
5. The test in one semester is expressed in 1 credit unit (3 days for test preparation and 1 day for the exam).
6. Intermediate certifications are also taken into account when granting credits in educational programs implemented in accordance with educational standards, and allocated credits are determined by subject.
7. Final certifications are issued on the basis of the weekly loading calculation. In this case, 1 week corresponds to 1.8 credits.
8. The test in one semester is expressed in 1 credit unit (3 days for test preparation and 1 day for the exam).
9. In educational programs implemented in accordance with educational standards, intermediate attestations are also taken into account when granting credits, and allocated credits are determined by subject.
10. Credit for final certificates is given based on the weekly load. In this case, 1 week corresponds to 1.8 credits.

Based on the method of calculating these credit units -

1 credit = 27 astronomical hours = 30 academic hours duration is 40 minutes;

1 week (internship or other educational work) = 54 academic hours = 1.8 credits;

In the same form, the labor intensity of the final certification is calculated:

1 week corresponds to 1.8 credit units;

Academic year - 30 weeks, they 60 credits;

Sessions are expressed in credits. That is, 1 test in 1 semester is expressed in 1 credit course unit.

The use of the credit-module system in higher education provides an opportunity to effectively organize the educational process:

- Organization of the educational process with individual goals, creates an opportunity for students to draw up individual study plans, to freely determine the sequence of learning subjects, to independently draw up a schedule of educational activities in the semester;

- Stimulates the scoring system for evaluating the results of students' educational activities;

- educational content ensures the formation of curriculum, programs and standards and their continuous development;

- giving academic freedom to professors and teachers, including the right to freely choose teaching methods;

- increases the cost of education and the economic efficiency of the work of professors and teachers;

- helps in the formation of the income and expenditure budget of the educational structures of the institution.

The characteristics of the credit-module system ensure the organization of the individual-targeted educational process and the evaluation of the educational process based on the advanced principles of pedagogical management on the basis of the score-rating system.

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